

A Deep Learning Framework for Trial-Level Assessment of Task-Evoked fNIRS Motor Activation Quality

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ABSTRACT

Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) provides a non-invasive means of measuring task-evoked cortical haemodynamic activity and is widely used in motor neuroscience and neurorehabilitation research. This study proposes a trial-level framework for modelling motor activation quality from fNIRS haemodynamic signals using physiologically motivated pseudo-labelling and deep learning-based classification. Oxy-haemoglobin (HbO) and deoxy-haemoglobin (HbR) responses were segmented into task-related trials, baseline-corrected using the pre-task interval, and used to compute activation-quality scores based on HbO task-related change, HbO peak amplitude, HbO area under the curve, and HbR response. Trials with high activation scores were labelled as good activation responses, trials with low scores were labelled as poor activation responses, and middle-range uncertain trials were excluded to reduce pseudo-label ambiguity. Three deep learning architectures were evaluated: CNN-BiLSTM, ResNet1D, and a compact temporal convolutional network termed HTCNet. Subject-independent performance was assessed using leave-one-subject-out validation. From 200 extracted task trials, 161 trials were retained after excluding uncertain responses, comprising 81 poor-activation and 80 good-activation trials. HTCNet achieved the best performance, with 89.44% accuracy, 89.44% balanced accuracy, 90.00% sensitivity for good activation, 88.89% specificity for poor activation, and an F1-score of 89.44%. ResNet1D achieved 85.09% accuracy, while CNN-BiLSTM achieved 70.81%. These findings suggest that pseudo-labelled task-evoked fNIRS haemodynamic patterns can be used to model trial-level motor activation response quality. The framework may support future fNIRS-based motor assessment and neurorehabilitation monitoring after validation in clinical populations.

1. Introduction

Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) is a non-invasive neuroimaging technique for measuring task-related cortical haemodynamic activity through changes in oxy-haemoglobin (HbO) and deoxy-haemoglobin (HbR) concentration [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. The portability, non-invasive nature, and relative tolerance of fNIRS to naturalistic movement make the modality useful for motor neuroscience, brain-computer interface (BCI) research, and neurorehabilitation monitoring [2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]. In motor-task studies, fNIRS is commonly applied to investigate task-evoked cortical activation across motor-related brain regions [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 10, 11, 12]. The physiological basis of this measurement is neurovascular coupling, whereby increased neuronal activity leads to changes in oxygen demand, cerebral blood flow, and haemoglobin concentrations [2, 11, 12, 13, 14]. As a result, task-evoked activation is typically associated with an increase in HbO and a corresponding decrease in HbR [10, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. This process is illustrated conceptually in Figure 1.

A common approach in task-based fNIRS analysis involves averaging haemodynamic responses across repeated trials or blocks to estimate a representative activation pattern for a subject or group [1, 2, 3, 12]. Block-averaged responses are valuable because random noise is reduced

and canonical task-evoked HbO/HbR changes can be visualised. However, trial averaging may obscure important trial-to-trial variability. Repeated motor-task trials from the same subject may differ in amplitude, timing, signal quality, and physiological consistency, even under an unchanged task protocol. Such variability may arise from differences in attention, fatigue, movement execution, neurovascular response dynamics, systemic physiology, or measurement noise [10]. Therefore, an averaged response may not fully represent the reliability or quality of individual task-evoked activation patterns.

This issue is particularly relevant in neuroscience and rehabilitation contexts, where the occurrence of a motor task does not necessarily guarantee a strong or physiologically meaningful cortical response. During motor rehabilitation, for example, a patient may attempt or perform a movement while the associated cortical activation remains weak, delayed, inconsistent, or contaminated by noise. In such situations, the relevant question extends beyond task occurrence and concerns the quality of the cortical haemodynamic response. Trial-level assessment of activation quality may therefore provide complementary information to conventional averaged activation analysis by identifying strong, weak, or unreliable responses across repeated task attempts.

Existing fNIRS classification studies have made important contributions to BCI and motor decoding by discriminating between task conditions, activity states, or mental

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Figure 1: Conceptual illustration of fNIRS-based neurovascular coupling during task-evoked cortical activation. Increased neuronal activity produces increased oxygen demand and local blood-flow changes, typically observed as an increase in oxy-haemoglobin (HbO) and a decrease in deoxy-haemoglobin (HbR). The quality of this task-evoked haemodynamic response forms the basis of the proposed motor activation quality assessment framework.

strategies [7, 24]. Deep learning methods have further improved fNIRS decoding by learning temporal and spatial patterns directly from haemodynamic signals, reducing dependence on handcrafted feature extraction [24, 25]. However, classification frameworks are commonly designed to predict task labels or task categories. Less attention has been given to classification frameworks that estimate the quality of the haemodynamic activation response at the trial level. This distinction is important because task classification addresses the performed or intended condition, whereas activation-quality classification addresses the strength and physiological consistency of the cortical response during the task.

A trial-level framework for motor activation quality assessment from fNIRS haemodynamic signals is proposed in this study by combining HbO/HbR-based activation-quality scoring with subject-independent deep learning classification. Instead of classifying rest versus task, individual task trials are segmented into analysis windows, baseline-corrected using the pre-task interval, and characterised according to the strength and consistency of their haemodynamic activation response. The activation-quality score is derived from interpretable response characteristics, including HbO task-related change, HbO peak amplitude, HbO area under the curve, and HbR response. In the absence of externally validated clinical activation-quality labels, this score is used as a physiologically motivated pseudo-labelling scheme: trials with clearly high scores are labelled as good activation responses, trials with clearly low scores are labelled as poor activation responses, and middle-range responses are treated as uncertain and excluded from model training and testing to reduce label ambiguity. Accordingly, the terms “good activation” and “poor activation” refer to high-score and low-score haemodynamic responses defined by the proposed scoring scheme, rather than clinically validated categories of motor impairment or recovery.

The proposed framework is evaluated using subject-independent leave-one-subject-out validation. This validation strategy assesses whether learned haemodynamic patterns generalise to unseen subjects, rather than only to trials from subjects represented during training. Three deep learning architectures are compared: a CNN-BiLSTM model, a one-dimensional residual network (ResNet1D), and a compact Haemodynamic Temporal Convolutional Network (HTCNet). Through this comparison, the study examines how recurrent temporal modelling, residual temporal convolution, and compact temporal convolution perform when applied to trial-level HbO/HbR activation-quality classification.

The main contributions of this study are as follows. First, a trial-level fNIRS motor activation quality assessment framework is introduced to characterise the strength and physiological quality of task-evoked haemodynamic responses rather than only task occurrence. Second, a physiologically motivated pseudo-labelling strategy is developed using interpretable HbO/HbR activation characteristics, while explicitly treating the resulting labels as derived activation-quality classes. Third, multiple deep learning architectures are evaluated under subject-independent validation to assess generalisation across participants. Finally, subject-level activation quality profiling is provided as a potential direction for future fNIRS-based monitoring of neural engagement in motor neuroscience and neurorehabilitation applications.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II presents the methods, including the dataset, experimental protocol, trial segmentation, activation-quality scoring, pseudo-label generation, deep learning architectures, training configuration, subject-independent validation, and evaluation metrics. Section III presents the results, including trial-level activation-quality labelling, model comparison, confusion-matrix analysis, subject-level activation-quality

profiling, and representative haemodynamic responses. Section IV discusses the main findings, interpretation of model performance, clinical relevance, limitations, and future work. Section V concludes the paper.

2. Materials and Methods

This section describes the dataset, experimental protocol, trial segmentation procedure, activation-quality scoring strategy, pseudo-label generation, deep learning models, validation method, and evaluation metrics used for trial-level motor activation quality classification.

2.1. Dataset

The study used a publicly available fNIRS motor-task dataset published by Akhter *et al.* [26], with acquisition and methodological details described in the associated study [24]. The dataset contains haemodynamic recordings acquired during repetitive hand-gripping motor activity. The available data include raw optical measurements, processed haemodynamic signals, and labelled recordings. In this study, the processed and labelled oxy-haemoglobin (HbO) and deoxy-haemoglobin (HbR) concentration-change signals were used to construct trial-level samples for motor activation quality classification.

For each participant, HbO and HbR data were provided as labelled time-series recordings. The labels indicated rest and activity periods, allowing task blocks to be identified automatically. The sampling frequency was set to 10.1725 Hz according to the dataset description. Each participant contributed one continuous recording containing an initial rest period, repeated hand-gripping activity blocks, inter-trial rest periods, and a final rest period. The dataset was used to construct trial-level haemodynamic samples for classifying motor activation quality.

2.2. Experimental Protocol

The experimental paradigm is shown in Figure 2. Each participant completed an initial 30 s resting period before the motor-task trials began. The task phase consisted of ten repeated trials. Each trial contained a 10 s hand-gripping activity period followed by a 20 s rest period. After the ten task trials, a final 30 s rest period was recorded. The total recording duration for each participant was therefore 360 s.

During the rest periods, participants remained relaxed and did not perform the hand-gripping activity. During the activity periods, participants performed repetitive voluntary hand-gripping. The repeated-block design enabled task-evoked haemodynamic responses to be extracted at the trial level, allowing the quality of individual activation responses to be examined rather than relying only on a single averaged response per participant.

2.3. Trial Segmentation and Signal Representation

The labelled time-series recordings were segmented into individual task-related trials using the detected onset of each activity block. The full experimental paradigm is shown in Figure 2; however, the trial-level analysis window was

defined separately around each activity onset. For each detected activity onset, a 25 s trial window was extracted from 5 s before onset to 20 s after onset. This 25 s window does not indicate that the hand-gripping task lasted 25 s. Rather, it consisted of a 5 s pre-task baseline, the 10 s hand-gripping task period, and a 10 s post-task recovery interval:

$-5 \text{ s} \leq t < 0 \text{ s}$: baseline,

$0 \text{ s} \leq t \leq 10 \text{ s}$: task,

$10 \text{ s} < t \leq 20 \text{ s}$: post-task recovery.

The post-task interval was included because fNIRS haemodynamic responses are delayed and may continue to evolve after the motor task has ended. The relative trial time was therefore defined as:

$$t \in [-5, 20] \text{ s}.$$

The pre-task interval from -5 s to 0 s was used for baseline correction. For each trial and each channel, the mean value within the baseline interval was subtracted from the full trial window. This produced baseline-corrected haemodynamic responses:

$$\Delta HbO(t, c) = HbO(t, c) - \overline{HbO}_{baseline}(c),$$

$$\Delta HbR(t, c) = HbR(t, c) - \overline{HbR}_{baseline}(c),$$

where t denotes time within the trial and c denotes the fNIRS channel.

Each trial was represented as a feature-by-time sequence. Since 20 HbO channels and 20 HbR channels were used, each trial contained 40 haemodynamic features at each time point:

$$X_i \in \mathbb{R}^{40 \times T},$$

where X_i represents the i -th trial and T is the number of time samples in the 25 s trial window. This representation preserved the temporal evolution of the haemodynamic response while retaining channel-wise HbO and HbR information.

2.4. Motor Activation Quality Score

A physiologically motivated activation-quality score was computed for each segmented trial. The aim of this score was to quantify the strength and quality of the task-evoked haemodynamic response. A stronger motor activation response was expected to show a clearer HbO increase during the task period and an appropriate HbR response. The score was therefore based on haemodynamic features extracted from the baseline-corrected trial response.

For each trial, the mean HbO and HbR responses were first computed across the 20 channels. The following trial-level features were then extracted:

- HbO task-minus-baseline response: mean HbO change during the task window.

Figure 2: Experimental paradigm for the motor-task fNIRS recording. Each participant completed an initial 30 s rest period, followed by ten repeated task trials. Each trial consisted of 10 s of hand-gripping activity followed by 20 s of rest. A final 30 s rest period concluded the session, giving a total recording duration of 360 s per participant.

- HbO peak amplitude: maximum HbO response during the task window.
- HbO area under the curve: accumulated HbO response during the task window.
- HbR task-minus-baseline response: mean HbR change during the task window.

The task window was defined as 0–10 s relative to activation onset. The activation-quality score was calculated as:

$$S_i = z(\Delta HbO_{\text{task},i}) + z(\Delta HbO_{\text{peak},i}) + z(\Delta HbO_{\text{AUC},i}) - z(\Delta HbR_{\text{task},i}) \quad (1)$$

where S_i is the activation-quality score for trial i , and $z(\cdot)$ denotes z-score normalisation across trials. The HbO-related terms reward stronger task-evoked oxygenation responses, while the HbR term penalises responses inconsistent with the expected decrease in deoxy-haemoglobin during functional activation.

This score was not intended to serve as a clinical ground-truth label. Instead, it provided a physiologically interpretable method for separating trials with clearly strong haemodynamic activation from trials with weak or poor activation.

2.5. Good/Poor Activation Pseudo-Label Generation

The activation-quality score was used to generate pseudo-labels for supervised classification. Trials with the lowest

activation-quality scores were labelled as poor activation responses, while trials with the highest scores were labelled as good activation responses. To reduce ambiguity, middle-range trials were excluded from model training and testing.

The bottom 40% of activation-quality scores were labelled as poor activation, and the top 40% were labelled as good activation. The middle 20% of trials were labelled as uncertain and removed from the classification dataset:

$$\text{Poor} = S_i \leq Q_{0.40},$$

$$\text{Good} = S_i \geq Q_{0.60},$$

where $Q_{0.40}$ and $Q_{0.60}$ represent the 40th and 60th percentile thresholds of the activation-quality score distribution.

A total of 200 task trials were extracted from the 20 participants. After excluding uncertain middle-range responses, 161 trials were retained for classification. These consisted of 81 poor-activation trials and 80 good-activation trials. The exclusion of uncertain trials was used to reduce pseudo-label noise and create a clearer binary classification problem.

2.6. Deep Learning Models

Three candidate deep learning architectures were evaluated within the proposed motor activation-quality assessment framework: CNN-BiLSTM, ResNet1D, and HTCNet. All models received the same baseline-corrected HbO/HbR trial representation as input. Each input trial was represented as a 40-feature time series, corresponding to 20 HbO channels and 20 HbR channels extracted from the 25 s trial window.

The overall model comparison is shown in Figure 3. A shared input representation was used for all models to

ensure that differences in classification performance were attributable to the model architecture rather than differences in signal representation. Similarly, all models used the same binary classification objective, in which each retained trial was classified as either good or poor motor activation.

The CNN-BiLSTM model combined temporal convolutional feature extraction with recurrent sequence modelling. Two one-dimensional convolutional blocks were first used to extract local haemodynamic response patterns from the trial sequence. The resulting temporal feature representation was then passed to a bidirectional long short-term memory (BiLSTM) layer with 64 hidden units. The BiLSTM layer was included to model forward and backward temporal dependencies within the haemodynamic response. A dense embedding layer with 32 units was then applied before the final classification stage.

The ResNet1D model was implemented as a residual temporal convolutional architecture. After an initial temporal convolutional stem, the model used residual blocks with skip connections. These skip connections allowed temporal features to propagate across layers and reduced the risk of degradation during deeper feature learning. Global average pooling was then applied to summarise the learned temporal feature maps before dense embedding and classification.

The HTCNet model was implemented as a compact temporal convolutional network. It used three temporal convolutional blocks to learn task-evoked haemodynamic patterns directly from the trial-level fNIRS sequence. Unlike the CNN-BiLSTM model, HTCNet did not include recurrent sequence modelling. Unlike the ResNet1D model, HTCNet did not use residual skip connections. Instead, temporal convolutional feature extraction and feature aggregation were used to provide a simpler architecture for activation-quality classification.

By evaluating CNN-BiLSTM, ResNet1D, and HTCNet under the same segmentation, pseudo-labelling, and subject-independent validation procedure, the study compared recurrent temporal modelling, residual temporal convolution, and compact temporal convolution within a common fNIRS motor activation-quality assessment framework.

2.7. Training Configuration

All deep learning models were trained using the same optimisation settings to ensure a fair comparison between CNN-BiLSTM, ResNet1D, and HTCNet. The training hyperparameters are summarised in Table 1. The Adam optimiser was used with a maximum of 60 epochs, a mini-batch size of 16, and an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-3} . The training data were shuffled at every epoch. Dropout regularisation was included within the model architectures to reduce overfitting.

For leave-one-subject-out validation, model training was repeated independently for each fold, with one subject held out for testing and the remaining subjects used for training.

2.8. Subject-Independent Validation

Model performance was evaluated using leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) validation. In each validation fold, data

Table 1

Training hyperparameters used for all deep learning models.

Hyperparameter	Value
Optimiser	Adam
Maximum epochs	60
Mini-batch size	16
Initial learning rate	1×10^{-3}
Shuffle strategy	Every epoch
Validation strategy	Leave-one-subject-out
Input representation	$40 \times T$ HbO/HbR sequence
Dropout	Model-dependent, 0.20–0.30

from one participant were used as the test set, while data from the remaining participants were used for training. This process was repeated until every participant had served once as the unseen test participant. The predictions from all folds were then combined to compute the final performance metrics.

LOSO validation was selected because it provides a subject-independent estimate of model generalisation. This is important for fNIRS analysis because haemodynamic responses can vary substantially across participants due to anatomical, physiological, and signal-quality differences. A model that performs well under LOSO validation is therefore more likely to have learned patterns that generalise across individuals rather than patterns specific to participants seen during training.

2.9. Evaluation Metrics

Classification performance was assessed using accuracy, balanced accuracy, good-class sensitivity, poor-class specificity, good-class precision, F1-score, and confusion matrices. Accuracy measured the overall proportion of correctly classified trials:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Good-class sensitivity measured the proportion of true good activation trials correctly classified as good:

$$\text{Sensitivity}_{\text{Good}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

Poor-class specificity measured the proportion of true poor activation trials correctly classified as poor:

$$\text{Specificity}_{\text{Poor}} = \frac{TN}{TN + FP}$$

Good-class precision measured the reliability of good activation predictions:

$$\text{Precision}_{\text{Good}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

The F1-score for the good class was computed as:

Figure 3: Comparison of the three candidate deep learning architectures evaluated within the proposed motor activation-quality assessment framework. A shared baseline-corrected fNIRS trial sequence was used as input for all models, consisting of 20 HbO and 20 HbR channels across the 25 s trial window. The CNN-BiLSTM model combined temporal convolution with bidirectional recurrent sequence modelling, the ResNet1D model used residual temporal convolutional blocks, and HTCNet used compact temporal convolutional feature extraction. All models used the same good/poor activation classification objective.

$$F1_{\text{Good}} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision}_{\text{Good}} \times \text{Sensitivity}_{\text{Good}}}{\text{Precision}_{\text{Good}} + \text{Sensitivity}_{\text{Good}}}$$

Balanced accuracy (*BA*) was computed as the average of good-class sensitivity and poor-class specificity:

$$BA = \frac{\text{Sensitivity}_{\text{Good}} + \text{Specificity}_{\text{Poor}}}{2}$$

A binomial test was also used to determine whether the observed classification accuracy was significantly above the 50% chance level expected for a balanced binary classification problem. Statistical significance was reported at $p < 0.001$.

3. Results

This section presents the trial-level activation-quality labelling outcome, model comparison results, confusion-matrix analysis, subject-level activation-quality profiles, and representative haemodynamic responses for good and poor activation trials.

3.1. Trial-Level Activation Quality Labelling

A total of 200 task trials were extracted from the 20 participants, corresponding to ten detected activity trials per participant. Each trial was assigned an activation-quality

score based on the strength and direction of the baseline-corrected HbO and HbR responses during the task period. Trials in the lower 40% of the activation-quality score distribution were labelled as poor activation, while trials in the upper 40% were labelled as good activation. The middle 20% of trials were treated as uncertain and excluded from model training and evaluation to reduce pseudo-label ambiguity.

After excluding uncertain middle-range trials, 161 trials were retained for classification. The retained dataset consisted of 81 poor-activation trials and 80 good-activation trials, producing an approximately balanced binary classification problem. The retained trials therefore represented cases with clearer haemodynamic separation between weak and strong motor activation responses.

Figure 4 shows the activation-quality score distribution after pseudo-label generation. The retained good and poor activation trials formed two distinct groups, supporting the use of the derived labels for supervised classification.

3.2. Model Comparison

The classification performance of the three candidate deep learning architectures is summarised in Table 2. The models were evaluated using the same trial segmentation, activation-quality pseudo-labels, input representation, and leave-one-subject-out validation procedure. This ensured that differences in performance reflected the model architecture rather than differences in data preparation or validation strategy.

Figure 4: Distribution of trial-level activation-quality scores after pseudo-label generation. Trials with low scores were labelled as poor activation, trials with high scores were labelled as good activation, and middle-range uncertain trials were excluded from classification.

Table 2
Model comparison under leave-one-subject-out validation.

Model	Accuracy (%)	Balanced Accuracy (%)	Sensitivity: Good (%)	Specificity: Poor (%)	Precision: Good (%)	F1-score: Good (%)
CNN-BiLSTM	70.81	70.79	67.50	74.07	72.00	69.68
ResNet1D	85.09	85.08	83.75	86.42	85.90	84.81
HTCNet	89.44	89.44	90.00	88.89	88.89	89.44

HTCNet achieved the highest overall performance, with an accuracy of 89.44% and a balanced accuracy of 89.44%. ResNet1D also achieved strong performance, with an accuracy of 85.09% and balanced accuracy of 85.08%. The CNN-BiLSTM model produced the lowest performance among the three models, with an accuracy of 70.81%. All models performed significantly above the 50% chance level using a binomial test, with $p < 0.001$.

The strongest performance was obtained by HTCNet, indicating that compact temporal convolutional feature extraction was sufficient to capture discriminative haemodynamic activation-quality patterns in the retained trial-level dataset. The performance of ResNet1D also suggests that residual temporal convolution can effectively model trial-level fNIRS activation patterns. The lower performance of CNN-BiLSTM indicates that adding recurrent sequence modelling did not improve classification in this experimental setting.

3.3. Confusion Matrix Analysis

Confusion matrices were used to examine the class-specific behaviour of each model. The confusion-matrix summary is shown in Table 3. The CNN-BiLSTM model correctly classified 60 poor-activation trials and 54 good-activation trials, but misclassified 21 poor trials as good and 26 good trials as poor. This indicates moderate class separation and relatively balanced error across both classes.

ResNet1D improved class separation, correctly classifying 70 poor-activation trials and 67 good-activation trials. The model misclassified 11 poor trials as good and 13 good trials as poor. This produced stronger class-specific performance than CNN-BiLSTM, showing that residual temporal convolution improved the discrimination of good and poor activation responses.

HTCNet produced the strongest confusion-matrix result. The model correctly classified 72 poor-activation trials and 72 good-activation trials, with 9 poor trials misclassified as good and 8 good trials misclassified as poor. This indicates balanced performance across both classes, with high sensitivity for good activation and high specificity for poor activation.

Table 3 shows that HTCNet produced the fewest misclassifications in both directions. This is important for activation-quality assessment because both error types are meaningful. Misclassifying poor activation as good may overestimate motor-cortex engagement, while misclassifying good activation as poor may underestimate a meaningful activation response.

3.4. Subject-Level Activation Quality Profile

Subject-level activation-quality profiles were examined to show how the proportion of good activation trials varied across participants. Each participant originally completed ten task trials; however, the number of retained labelled

Table 3

Confusion-matrix summary for the three deep learning models.

Model	Poor → Poor	Poor → Good	Good → Poor	Good → Good
CNN-BiLSTM	60	21	26	54
ResNet1D	70	11	13	67
HTCNet	72	9	8	72

Figure 5: Subject-level motor activation quality profile. Bars show the percentage of retained labelled trials identified as good activation for each participant. Each participant originally completed ten task trials, but uncertain middle-range activation responses were excluded before classification; therefore, variation in subject-level percentages reflects retained labelled trials rather than missing task recordings.

trials varied after pseudo-label generation because uncertain middle-range activation responses were excluded before classification. Therefore, the subject-level percentages represent the proportion of retained labelled trials identified as good activation, rather than the proportion of all originally recorded trials.

Figure 5 shows inter-subject variability in motor activation quality. Some participants showed a high proportion of good activation trials, while others showed lower proportions or no retained good-activation trials. This subject-level profile complements the trial-level classification results by providing a participant-specific view of haemodynamic response quality.

3.5. Example Good and Poor Haemodynamic Responses

Representative examples of good and poor activation trials were examined to support physiological interpretation of the pseudo-labels. A good activation response was characterised by a clearer task-related HbO increase and an associated HbR decrease during or shortly after the task period. This pattern is consistent with the expected haemodynamic response during task-evoked cortical activation.

Poor activation trials showed weaker or less consistent haemodynamic responses. In these trials, the HbO increase was smaller, delayed, or less clearly sustained during the

task period, and the HbR response was less consistent with the expected task-evoked decrease. These weaker responses resulted in lower activation-quality scores and were labelled as poor activation.

Figure 6 illustrates representative good and poor haemodynamic responses. These examples support the interpretation that the classification task was based on physiologically meaningful trial-level haemodynamic differences rather than arbitrary class assignment.

4. Discussion

This study presented a trial-level framework for assessing motor activation quality from task-evoked fNIRS haemodynamic responses. Rather than treating the task only as an activity-detection problem, the analysis focused on whether individual task trials produced good or poor cortical haemodynamic activation responses. This framing is important because task performance or task occurrence does not necessarily imply a strong or physiologically meaningful cortical response. Trial-level assessment can therefore provide complementary information to conventional block-averaged fNIRS analysis by highlighting variability in haemodynamic response quality across repeated motor-task attempts.

Figure 6: Representative baseline-corrected haemodynamic responses from Subject 1 for (a) a good activation trial and (b) a poor activation trial. The red curve represents the mean oxy-haemoglobin response (ΔHbO), while the blue curve represents the mean deoxy-haemoglobin response (ΔHbR). The grey shaded region indicates the 10 s motor-task period from task onset to task offset. The good activation example shows a clearer task-related increase in ΔHbO with a corresponding decrease in ΔHbR , whereas the poor activation example shows a weaker and less consistent haemodynamic activation pattern.

4.1. Main Findings

The main finding was that trial-level motor activation quality could be classified from baseline-corrected HbO/HbR fNIRS responses using deep temporal learning models. From 200 extracted task trials, 161 trials were retained after excluding uncertain middle-range responses. The retained dataset was approximately balanced, containing 81 poor-activation trials and 80 good-activation trials.

Among the three evaluated deep learning architectures, HTCNet achieved the strongest performance under leave-one-subject-out validation, with an accuracy of 89.44% and balanced accuracy of 89.44%. The model also achieved 90.00% sensitivity for good activation and 88.89% specificity for poor activation. ResNet1D also performed strongly, achieving 85.09% accuracy, while CNN-BiLSTM achieved 70.81% accuracy. These results indicate that temporal convolutional feature extraction was effective for distinguishing good and poor haemodynamic activation responses in the retained trial-level dataset.

The confusion-matrix analysis further showed that HTCNet produced the most balanced class-specific performance. The model correctly classified 72 of 80 good-activation trials and 72 of 81 poor-activation trials. This balance is important because both types of misclassification have practical implications. Misclassifying poor activation as good may overestimate cortical engagement, while misclassifying good activation as poor may underestimate the presence of a meaningful motor response.

4.2. Interpretation of Model Performance

The superior performance of HTCNet suggests that compact temporal convolutional learning was well suited to

the structure of the trial-level fNIRS data. fNIRS haemodynamic responses evolve gradually over time, and discriminative information may be contained in local temporal patterns such as the onset, rise, peak, and recovery of HbO and HbR signals. One-dimensional temporal convolutional layers can learn these local response patterns directly from the trial sequence while maintaining a relatively compact model structure.

The strong performance of ResNet1D also supports the usefulness of convolutional temporal feature learning. Residual connections can help preserve temporal information across layers and allow deeper feature extraction. However, in the present experiment, ResNet1D did not outperform HTCNet. This suggests that additional residual complexity was not necessary for the retained dataset and that a simpler temporal convolutional architecture was sufficient to capture the relevant haemodynamic activation-quality patterns.

The CNN-BiLSTM model achieved lower performance than the convolutional models. Although BiLSTM layers are useful for modelling long-range dependencies in sequence data, the relatively small number of retained trials may have limited the benefit of recurrent sequence modelling. The higher complexity of the CNN-BiLSTM architecture may also have increased the risk of overfitting under subject-independent validation. In contrast, HTCNet provided a better balance between model capacity and dataset size.

These findings should not be interpreted as showing that HTCNet is universally superior to ResNet1D or CNN-BiLSTM for all fNIRS applications. Model performance can vary depending on dataset size, task type, preprocessing choices, input representation, and validation strategy. Under the present experimental conditions, HTCNet achieved the

best balance of accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1-score.

4.3. Clinical Relevance

The proposed framework has potential relevance for neuroscience and neurorehabilitation because it focuses on the quality of the task-evoked haemodynamic response rather than only on task occurrence. In motor assessment and rehabilitation monitoring, the key question is often not only whether a participant attempted or performed a movement, but whether the movement was associated with meaningful cortical activation. A trial-level activation-quality framework may therefore support more informative monitoring of neural engagement during repeated motor-task attempts.

The subject-level activation-quality profiles also provide a potentially useful interpretation layer. Instead of reporting only a single group-level classification accuracy, the framework can summarise the proportion of retained trials showing good activation for each participant. Such information may help identify participants with consistent activation responses, variable activation responses, or predominantly weak responses. In future clinical applications, this type of subject-level profile may be useful for monitoring therapy engagement, response consistency, or longitudinal changes in motor-cortex activation.

The framework may also be useful for fNIRS data quality and trial selection. Task-based fNIRS recordings often contain trials with weak, noisy, delayed, or physiologically inconsistent responses. A trial-level activation-quality classifier could help identify trials that are less representative of reliable task-evoked cortical activation. This could complement conventional preprocessing and block-averaging approaches by providing an interpretable estimate of response quality at the level of individual task attempts.

However, the results should not be interpreted as evidence of clinical diagnostic ability. The labels used in this study were physiologically motivated pseudo-labels derived from HbO/HbR response characteristics, not clinician-provided impairment labels. In addition, the analysed dataset was not a clinical patient dataset. Therefore, the present framework should be viewed as a proof-of-concept approach for fNIRS-based motor activation quality assessment. Clinical relevance would require further validation using patient populations, clinician-rated motor assessments, and longitudinal rehabilitation data.

4.4. Limitations

Several limitations should be considered. First, the good and poor activation labels were pseudo-labels derived from haemodynamic response features rather than externally validated clinical labels. Although the pseudo-labelling strategy was physiologically motivated, it remains rule-based and depends on the selected activation-quality score. This means that the classification results reflect the ability of the models to learn the proposed activation-quality formulation, not necessarily clinically confirmed motor impairment or recovery status.

Second, middle-range activation responses were excluded to reduce pseudo-label ambiguity. This created a clearer binary classification problem but reduced the number of available trials from 200 to 161. The resulting dataset was suitable for proof-of-concept evaluation, but the reduced sample size may limit the robustness of deep learning model training. Future studies should examine whether uncertain trials can be handled through confidence-based classification, ordinal labelling, or regression-based activation-quality prediction rather than exclusion.

Third, the dataset contained only 20 participants. Although leave-one-subject-out validation provided a subject-independent evaluation, larger datasets are required to assess generalisability across broader populations. fNIRS signals can vary substantially between individuals due to differences in scalp-cortex distance, optode coupling, physiology, task execution, and neurovascular response. A larger and more diverse dataset would allow more reliable estimation of generalisation performance.

Fourth, the analysis used processed and labelled HbO/HbR signals. This allowed the study to focus on trial-level activation-quality classification, but the effect of preprocessing choices was not systematically examined. Different filtering, motion correction, short-channel regression, or haemodynamic conversion methods may influence activation features and classification performance. Future work should assess the stability of the proposed framework under different preprocessing pipelines.

Fifth, the study focused on one motor-task paradigm. Although the framework is conceptually applicable to other task-evoked fNIRS paradigms, the present results are specific to the analysed motor-task dataset. Additional validation is required using other motor tasks, motor imagery tasks, patient datasets, and multi-session recordings.

5. Conclusion

This study proposed a trial-level fNIRS motor activation quality assessment framework based on task-evoked HbO and HbR haemodynamic responses. Individual task trials were segmented, baseline-corrected, scored using physiologically motivated activation features, and labelled as good or poor activation responses after excluding uncertain middle-range trials. Three candidate deep learning architectures were evaluated under leave-one-subject-out validation. The compact temporal convolutional model, HTCNet, achieved the best performance, with 89.44% accuracy, 89.44% balanced accuracy, 90.00% sensitivity for good activation, and 88.89% specificity for poor activation. ResNet1D also performed strongly, while CNN-BiLSTM showed lower generalisation performance. These findings suggest that temporal convolutional learning can effectively capture discriminative haemodynamic response patterns associated with trial-level motor activation quality. The proposed framework provides a more interpretable direction for fNIRS-based motor assessment by moving beyond task occurrence and focusing on the quality of the cortical

haemodynamic response. Although further validation on clinical populations is required, the approach may support future neurorehabilitation monitoring, trial-level neural engagement assessment, and subject-level profiling of motor activation response quality.

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